

ISic2848

I.Sicily inscription 2848

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

volcanic (local, from Fuardo)

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Lipara

Place of origin (modern)

Lipari

Provenance

Contr. Diana

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Lipari, Museo Archeologico

Regionale Eoliano "Luigi Bernabò Brea", inventory 14218

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI334562

1. Θ (εοῖς) Κ (αταχθονίοις) .

2. Μυρτίδι Θε-

3. οδώρου

4. ἀπελευ-

5. θέρα ζησά [ση]

6. ἔτη λε' #⁷ΑΤΕ

7. #⁷#⁷#⁷ΑΜΗΤ#⁷ Ι

8.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645242
PHI 334562

Bibliography

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 45.1381.79

Bernabò Brea, L., Cavalier, M., Campagna, L. 2003. Meligunìs Lipára. XII. Le iscrizioni lapidarie greche e latine delle isole eolie. Palermo. At 459

Bernabò Brea, L., Cavalier, M. 1994. Meligunis Lipara VII. Lipari. Contrada Diana. Scavo XXXVI in proprietà Zagami (1975-1984). Palermo. At no.79 pl.130

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